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Abbreviations

€	Euro
AAI	Authentication and Authorisation Infrastructure
APC	Article Processing Charge
BPC	Book Processing Charge
CERN	European Organisation for Nuclear Research
CoARA	Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment
CRIS	Current Research Information Systems
DMP	Data Management Plan
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
EOSC-SB	EOSC Steering Board
ERA	European Research Area
ESFRI	European Strategy Forum on Research Infrastructures
EuroHPC	European High-Performance Computing
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable
FTE	Full-time Equivalent
ERA	European Research Area
EU	European Union
IPR	Intellectual Property Rights
K	Thousand
M	Million
PID	Persistent Identifier
Q	Question
R&I	Research and Innovation
RFO	Research-funding Organisation
RPO	Research-performing Organisation
SESAME	Synchrotron-light for Experimental Science and Applications in the Middle East

Executive Summary

This report offers an *Analysis of the Survey on National Contributions to EOSC and Open Science 2023* and is deliverable D2.2 by Technopolis Group Belgium under the EOSC Track project. The analysis is based on responses by country members of the EOSC Steering Board to the *Survey on National Contributions to EOSC and Open Science 2023* and systematically addresses the questions related to national policies, financial strategies, national monitoring, and investments for each of the categories relevant for Open Science identified in the *Monitoring Framework for National Contributions to EOSC*. These categories include publications, data, software, services, infrastructure, skills/training, assessment, and engagement. A total of 32 countries (including 24 countries from the European Union) responded to Survey 2023 and provided not only direct responses to the survey questions but often additional comments to clarify and contextualise their survey responses. The responses to Survey 2023 are openly available in the EOSC Open Science Observatory and EOSC Observatory Zenodo Community.

1. Introduction

This report offers an *Analysis of the Survey on National Contributions to EOSC and Open Science 2023* and is deliverable D2 of the subcontract to Technopolis Group Belgium under the EOSC Track project [1]. The survey was developed by the EOSC Future project [2] and EOSC Steering Board (EOSC-SB) [3] to monitor policies, practices, and impacts related to EOSC and Open Science at national and institutional levels in Europe. The survey is targeted at the members of EOSC-SB and runs annually whereby a pilot survey was conducted in 2021 [4] and the first full survey was conducted in 2022 [5]. The survey data [6] and analysis [7] for 2021 and data [8] and analysis [9] for 2022 are available in the EOSC Observatory Zenodo Community [10].

The survey for 2023 is based on the first version of the *Monitoring Framework for National Contributions to EOSC* [11] which consists of indicators for policies and practices across eight categories relevant for EOSC and Open Science including publications, data, software, services, infrastructure, skills/training, assessment, and engagement as shown in Table 1. The indicators for policies consist of identifying countries which have a national policy, countries which have a financial strategy, research-performing organisations (RPOs) which have a policy, and research-funding organisations (RFOs) which have a policy on each of the categories. The indicators for practices consist of countries with a national monitoring, countries with use cases, countries with investments, and outputs for the countries for each of the categories.

	Policies	Practices
Publications	Countries with a National Policy	Countries with National Monitoring
Data	Countries with a Financial Strategy	Countries with Use Case
Software	Country RPOs with a Policy	Country Investments
Services	Country RFOs with a Policy	Country Outputs
Infrastructure		
Skills/Training		
Assessment		
Engagement		

Table 1: Monitoring Framework for National Contributions to EOSC

Survey 2023 [12] was published in the EOSC Open Science Observatory [13] on 17 January 2024 and ran until 01 July 2024 whereby 32 countries responded consisting of 24 of the 27

European Union (EU) countries and 8 non-EU countries as shown in Tables 2 and 3. The responding EU countries can be divided into 12 of the 12 non-widening countries and 12 of the 15 widening countries. The widening countries hereby are countries which are currently lagging behind in research and innovation (R&I) in Europe and which are being supported by the EU via targeted widening actions to upgrade their R&I systems to make them stronger and allow the EU as a whole to advance together [14] in line with the policy objectives of the European Research Area (ERA) [15]. This report is based on the data collected from Survey 2023 [16] which is openly available and exploitable in the EOSC Open Science Observatory.

Group		Country	Survey 2022	Survey 2023
EU (27)	Non-widening (12)	Austria	Yes	Yes
		Belgium	No	Yes
		Denmark	Yes	Yes
		Finland	Yes	Yes
		France	Yes	Yes
		Germany	Yes	Yes
		Italy	No	Yes
		Luxembourg	Yes	Yes
		Netherlands	Yes	Yes
		Republic of Ireland	Yes	Yes
		Spain	Yes	Yes
		Sweden	Yes	Yes
	Widening (15)	Bulgaria	Yes	Yes
		Croatia	Yes	Yes
		Cyprus	Yes	Yes
		Czech Republic	Yes	Yes
		Estonia	Yes	No
		Greece	Yes	Yes
		Hungary	Yes	No
		Latvia	Yes	Yes
		Lithuania	Yes	Yes
		Malta	Yes	Yes
		Poland	Yes	Yes
		Portugal	Yes	Yes
		Romania	No	No
		Slovakia	Yes	Yes
		Slovenia	Yes	Yes

Table 2: EU Countries Responding to Survey 2022 and Survey 2023

Group	Country	Survey 2022	Survey 2023
Non-EU	Armenia	Yes	Yes
	Bosnia and Herzegovina	Yes	No
	Faroe Islands	No	Yes
	Georgia	Yes	Yes
	Norway	Yes	Yes
	Serbia	Yes	Yes
	Switzerland	Yes	Yes
	Turkey	Yes	Yes
	Ukraine	Yes	No
	United Kingdom	No	Yes

Table 3: Non-EU Countries Responding to Survey 2022 and Survey 2023

It should be noted that while most of the countries responded to both Survey 2022 and Survey 2023, some of the countries only responded to either Survey 2022 or Survey 2023. This report provides an analysis of responses to 4 main types of questions in Survey 2023. These questions are on the 2 policy indicators of countries with a national policy and countries with a financial strategy as well as the 2 practice indicators of countries with a national monitoring and countries with investments for the monitoring framework categories. The report does not address the 2 policy indicators of RPOs with a policy and RFOs with a policy or the 2 practice indicators of countries with use cases and outputs for countries. Some data on these questions in Survey 2023 is available in the EOSC Open Science Observatory.

The report is structured around the monitoring framework categories and systematically addresses the 4 selected types of questions for each category. An analysis is provided for all survey respondents, followed by responding EU countries, and then responding non-widening versus widening countries. Each analysis is supported by graphs which focus on positive responses on existing policies, strategies, and investments whereby negative responses group countries which responded to the survey but either did not respond to the question or responded that there were no existing policies, strategies, and investments. The data behind the graphs in this report can be found in the EOSC Observatory Zenodo Community [17].

The report further offers an analysis of the total investments in EOSC and Open Science and a trend analysis focusing on the category of open access to publications. The total investments

are separated into millions of Euros and per 1000 full-time equivalent (FTE) researchers. A first trend analysis then compares the main policies and practices for open access to publications for EU countries and non-widening versus widening countries in 2023. A second trend analysis compares the progress of the main policies and practices for open access to publications for EU countries and non-widening versus widening countries from Survey 2022 to Survey 2023. The trend analysis serves as an initial study to address the impact of the policies and practices for EOSC and Open Science which may be included in future surveys based on the second version of the *Monitoring Framework for National Contributions to EOSC and Open Science* [18].

A clarification is needed for the responding countries of Belgium and Germany. Belgium recognises the competences in policymaking for EOSC and Open Science of the federal level and the three regions of the Flemish, Walloon, and Brussels-Capital Region as well as the three communities of the Flemish, French, and German-speaking communities under the Sovereign State. Only 1 response has been accepted from Belgium and an answer has been marked positive if there is a policy, financial strategy, or national monitoring in at least one region or community or at the federal level, while investments have been calculated at the federal level. Germany recognises 16 states under the Federal Republic. All responses from Germany are at the federal level and investments have been calculated at the federal level.

A clarification is also needed for the analysis of responses related to national investments which identifies groups of investments in thousands (K) and millions (M) of Euros (€) as well as per 1000 FTE researchers. The first group of investments from above 0 to 50 €K and from above 0 to 1 €M excludes empty responses and zero itself and thus means more than or above 0 and up to but not including 50 €K respectively 1 €M. The remaining groups from 50 to 1500 €K and from 1 to 150 €M mean from and including the first number (such as 50 €K) up to but not including the second number (such as 1500 €K). The number of FTE researchers in the countries has been taken from Eurostat for the year 2022 or the last updated year [19].

This report provides an overview analysis of key questions on policies and practices in Survey 2023. Interested readers are encouraged to dig deeper into the individual responses by the countries in the open data set and EOSC Open Science Observatory for Survey 2023.

2. Publications

2.1. Policies

2.1.1. National Policy on Open Access to Publications

The first main policy question on open access to publications in Survey 2023 is *Does your country have a national policy on open access to publications?* (Q1) followed by *Is this policy mandatory?* (Q1.1). A policy hereby refers to any policies, recommendations, regulations, or laws which are relevant for EOSC and Open Science and which are applicable at national or regional levels. 81% (26/32) of responding countries have a national policy whereby 39% (10/26) of those policies are mandatory as shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Countries with a National Policy on Open Access to Publications

87% (21/24) of responding EU countries have a national policy on open access to publications whereby 38% (8/21) are mandatory as shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2: EU Countries with a National Policy on Open Access to Publications

We see similar percentages for the non-widening and widening countries. 92% (11/12) of responding non-widening countries have a national policy on open access to publications whereby 36% (4/11) are mandatory and 83% (10/12) of responding widening countries have a national policy whereby 40% (4/10) are mandatory as shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3: Non-widening and Widening Countries with a National Policy on Open Access to Publications

In one country open access to publications is enshrined in a national law (such as a law on higher education). Some countries have dedicated national strategies, plans, or guidelines on open access to publications while others include this as part of (a) larger strategy, plan, or guidelines on Open Science which may be implemented via the national funding agencies.

2.1.2. Specific Policy on Immediate Open Access to Publications

One sub-question related to having a national policy on open access to publications is *Is there a specific policy on immediate open access to publications?* (Q1.3) followed by *Is this policy mandatory?* (Q1.3.1). 50% (16/32) of responding countries have a specific policy on immediate open access whereby 38% (6/16) of those policies are mandatory as shown in Figure 4.

Figure 4: Countries with a Specific Policy on Immediate Open Access to Publications

54% (13/24) of responding EU countries have a specific policy on immediate open access to publications whereby 31% (4/13) are mandatory as shown in Figure 5.

Figure 5: EU Countries with a Specific Policy on Immediate Open Access to Publications

We see similar percentages for the non-widening and widening countries. 58% (7/12) of responding non-widening countries have a specific policy on immediate open access to publications whereby 29% (2/7) are mandatory and 50% (6/12) of responding widening countries have a specific policy whereby 33% (2/6) are mandatory as shown in Figure 6.

Figure 6: Non-widening and Widening Countries with a Specific Policy on Immediate Open Access to Publication

Some countries may have a specific policy on immediate open access to publications as part of (a) larger strategy, plan, or guidelines on open access to publications. We note that immediate open access to publications is a core requirement of Plan S and that those national funding agencies aligned with Plan S will implement an immediate open access requirement.

2.1.3. Specific Policy on Retention of IPR on Publications

Another sub-question related to having a national policy on open access to publications is *Is there a specific policy on retention of IPR on publications?* (Q1.4) followed by *Is this policy mandatory?* (Q1.4.1). 38% (12/32) of responding countries have a specific policy on IPR retention whereby 58% (7/12) of those policies are mandatory as shown in Figure 7.

Figure 7: Countries with a Specific Policy on Retention of IPR on Publications

46% (11/24) of responding EU countries have a specific policy on retention of IPR on publications whereby 55% (6/11) are mandatory as shown in Figure 8.

Figure 8: EU Countries with a Specific Policy on Retention of IPR on Publications

We see differing percentages for the non-widening and widening countries. 67% (8/12) of responding non-widening countries have a specific policy on retention of IPR on publications whereby 50% (4/8) are mandatory and 25% (3/12) of responding widening countries have a specific policy whereby 67% (2/3) are mandatory as shown in Figure 9.

Figure 9: Non-widening and Widening Countries with a Specific Policy on Retention of IPR on Publications

Some countries have included retention of IPR on publications in a national law (such as a law on science or copyright act). Some countries may have a specific policy on retention of IPR on publications as part of (a) larger strategy, plan, or guidelines on open access to publications or Open Science. Retention of IPR on publications is a core requirement of Plan S and those national funding agencies aligned with Plan S will implement this IPR retention requirement.

2.1.4. Specific Policy on Open Licensing of Publications

A final sub-question related to having a national policy on open access to publications is *Is there a specific policy on open licensing of publications?* (Q1.5) followed by *Is this policy mandatory?* (Q1.5.1). 47% (15/32) of responding countries have a specific policy on IPR retention whereby 40% (6/15) of those policies are mandatory as shown in Figure 10.

Figure 10: Countries with a Specific Policy on Open Licensing of Publications

54% (13/24) of responding EU countries have a specific policy on open licensing of publications whereby 31% (4/13) are mandatory as shown in Figure 11.

Figure 11: EU Countries with a Specific Policy on Open Licensing of Publications

We see differing percentages for the non-widening and widening countries. 75% (9/12) of responding non-widening countries have a specific policy on open licensing of publications whereby 33% (3/9) are mandatory and 33% (4/12) of responding widening countries have a specific policy whereby 25% (1/4) are mandatory as shown in Figure 12.

Figure 12: Non-widening and Widening Countries with a Specific Policy on Open Licensing of Publications

Some countries may have a specific policy on open licensing of publications as part of (a) larger strategy, plan, or guidelines on open access to publications or Open Science. Some countries require an open licence (for research outputs) but do not specify the type of licence whereas other countries recommend specific types of national, Creative Commons, or software licences. Open licensing of publications is a core requirement of Plan S and those national funding agencies aligned with Plan S will implement this open licensing requirement.

2.1.5. Financial Strategy on Open Access to Publications

The second main policy question on open access to publications in Survey 2023 is *Does your country have a financial strategy on open access to publications?* (Q2). A financial strategy hereby refers to any self-standing strategy or strategy which is included in an overarching strategy at national or regional levels. 47% (15/32) of responding countries have a financial strategy as shown in Figure 13.

Figure 13: Countries with a Financial Strategy on Open Access to Publications

54% (13/24) of responding EU countries have a financial strategy on open access to publications as shown in Figure 14.

Figure 14: EU Countries with a Financial Strategy on Open Access to Publications

We see similar percentages for the non-widening and widening countries. 58% (7/12) of responding non-widening countries have a financial strategy on open access to publications and 50% (6/12) of responding widening countries have a financial strategy as shown in Figure 15.

Figure 15: Non-widening and Widening Countries with a Financial Strategy on Open Access to Publications

Financial strategies typically cover costs to finance agreements with publishers (such as read-and-publish and transformative agreements), open access journals and publishing platforms, research repositories, Current Research Information Systems (CRIS), promotion of open access to publications, publishing costs for articles in open access journals (whereby there may be a cap on individual article costs), and publishing costs for open access books. Some countries do not have a dedicated financial strategy on open access to publications but nevertheless fund costs related to open access to publications. Funding for open access to publications may be implemented via national funding agencies or research organisations.

2.2. Practices

2.2.1. National Monitoring on Open Access to Publications

The first main practice question on open access to publications in Survey 2023 is *Does your country have a national monitoring on open access to publications?* (Q49). National monitoring hereby refers to any monitoring of policies or practices at national or regional levels. 47% (15/32) of responding countries have a national monitoring as shown in Figure 16.

Figure 16: Countries with a National Monitoring on Open Access to Publications

46% (11/24) of responding EU countries have a national monitoring on open access to publications as shown in Figure 17.

Figure 17: EU Countries with a National Monitoring on Open Access to Publications

We see differing percentages for the non-widening and widening countries. 75% (9/12) of responding non-widening countries have a national monitoring on open access to publications and 17% (2/12) of responding widening countries have a national monitoring as shown in Figure 18.

Figure 18: Non-widening and Widening Countries with a National Monitoring on Open Access to Publications

Monitoring activities typically focus on the implementation and compliance of national and specific policies on open access to publications, open access agreements with publishers, and various statistics on open access publications. Information for monitoring activities can be collected via national libraries, research repositories, CRIS, digital observatories for Open Science, questionnaires, and specific monitoring applications such as Pure, Scopus, Unpaywall, and the OpenAIRE Graph. Some countries which do not yet have a national monitoring have stressed that setting up such a national monitoring is a future priority.

2.2.2. National Investments in Open Access to Publications

The second main practice question on open access to publications in Survey 2023 is *How much did your country financially invest in open access to publications in 2022 in millions of Euros?* (Q51). 38% (12/32) of responding countries are not investing or have not stated the amount of investments in open access to publications. 9% (3/32) of countries invested from above 0 to 50 €K, 16% (5/32) from 50 to 100 €K, 25% (8/32) from 100 to 250 €K, 3% (1/32) from 250 to 500 €K, and 6% (2/32) from 500 to 1000 €K per 1000 FTE researchers as shown in Figure 19. One country hereby has invested in open access to publications but has not provided official figures on the number of FTE researchers in the country in Eurostat.

Figure 19: Countries with National Investments in Open Access to Publications per 1000 FTE Researchers

There is a wide range of investments across responding EU countries in open access to publications. 38% (9/24) are not investing or have not stated the amount of investments in open access to publications. 8% (2/24) of EU countries invested from above 0 to 50 €K, 17% (4/24) from 50 to 100 €K, 29% (7/24) from 100 to 250 €K, 4% (1/24) from 250 to 500 €K, and 4% (1/24) from 500 to 1000 €K per 1000 FTE researchers as shown in Figure 20.

Figure 20: EU Countries with National Investments in Open Access to Publications per 1000 FTE Researchers

We see differing investments in open access to publications for the responding non-widening and widening countries. The non-widening countries show investments mostly from above 0 to 250 €K per 1000 FTE researchers while the widening countries show investments mostly from 50 to 250 €K per 1000 FTE researchers as shown in Figure 21.

Figure 21: Non-widening and Widening Countries with National Investments in Open Access to Publications per 1000 FTE Researchers

Many countries have noted that it is not possible to calculate the (exact) amount of investments in open access to publications because relevant data or the means to collect relevant data is not currently available. Investments in open access to publications typically include Article Processing Charges (APCs), Book Processing charges (BPCs), agreements with publishers (such as read-and-publish and transformative agreements), subsidies to open access journals and publishing platforms, and contributions to open access infrastructures.

3. Data

3.1. Policies

3.1.1. National Policy on Data Management

The first main policy question on data management in Survey 2023 is *Does your country have a national policy on data management?* (Q5) followed by *Is this policy mandatory?* (Q5.1). 63% (20/32) of responding countries have a national policy whereby 40% (8/20) of those policies are mandatory as shown in Figure 22.

Figure 22: Countries with a National Policy on Data Management

71% (17/24) of responding EU countries have a national policy on data management whereby 41% (7/17) are mandatory as shown in Figure 23.

Figure 23: EU Countries with a National Policy on Data Management

We see differing percentages for the non-widening and widening countries. 83% (10/12) of responding non-widening countries have a national policy on data management whereby 30% (3/10) are mandatory and 58% (7/12) of responding widening countries have a national policy whereby 57% (4/7) are mandatory as shown in Figure 24.

Figure 24: Non-widening and Widening Countries with a National Policy on Data Management

In some countries data management is enshrined in a national law (such as a law on higher education or laws related to support for research through public funds). Some countries note that the national policy on data management includes FAIR data and open data. The adoption of Data Management Plans (DMPs) is noted as especially important for data management.

3.1.2. National Policy on FAIR Data

The first main policy question on FAIR data in Survey 2023 is *Does your country have a national policy on FAIR data?* (Q9) followed by *Is this policy mandatory?* (Q9.1). 56% (18/32) of responding countries have a national policy whereby 33% (6/18) of those policies are mandatory as shown in Figure 25.

Figure 25: Countries with a National Policy on FAIR Data

62% (15/24) of responding EU countries have a national policy on FAIR data whereby 33% (5/15) are mandatory as shown in Figure 26.

Figure 26: EU Countries with a National Policy on FAIR Data

We see differing percentages for the non-widening and widening countries. 83% (10/12) of responding non-widening countries have a national policy on FAIR data whereby 20% (2/10) are mandatory and 42% (5/12) of responding widening countries have a national policy whereby 60% (3/5) are mandatory as shown in Figure 27.

Figure 27: Non-widening and Widening Countries with a National Policy on FAIR Data

Some countries note that the national policy on data management includes FAIR data and open data. In one case a country notes that national policies on data management predate the rise of the FAIR principles but that the policies nevertheless align with the FAIR principles. Data sets may be compliant with FAIR principles but DMPs may also be structured according to FAIR principles and research data repositories may be compliant with FAIR principles.

3.1.3. National Policy on Open Data

The first main policy question on open data in Survey 2023 is *Does your country have a national policy on open data?* (Q13) followed by *Is this policy mandatory?* (Q13.1). 69% (22/32) of responding countries have a national policy whereby 50% (11/22) of those policies are mandatory as shown in Figure 28.

Figure 28: Countries with a National Policy on Open Data

79% (19/24) of responding EU countries have a national policy on open data whereby 53% (10/19) are mandatory as shown in Figure 29.

Figure 29: EU Countries with a National Policy on Open Data

We see similar percentages for the non-widening and widening countries. 83% (10/12) of responding non-widening countries have a national policy on open data whereby 50% (5/10) are mandatory and 75% (9/12) of responding widening countries have a national policy whereby 56% (5/9) are mandatory as shown in Figure 30.

Figure 30: Non-widening and Widening Countries with a National Policy on Open Data

In some countries open data is enshrined in a national law (such as a law on a digital republic or a law on free access to information for public organisations). Some countries again note that the national policy on data management includes FAIR data and open data. Many countries note that open data has been integrated into the national implementation of European Directive 2019/1024 on open data and the re-use of public sector information [20].

3.1.4. Financial Strategy on Data Management

The second main policy question on data management in Survey 2023 is *Does your country have a financial strategy on data management?* (Q6). 41% (13/32) of responding countries have a financial strategy as shown in Figure 31.

Figure 31: Countries with a Financial Strategy on Data Management

46% (11/24) of responding EU countries have a financial strategy on data management as shown in Figure 32.

Figure 32: EU Countries with a Financial Strategy on Data Management

We see differing percentages for the non-widening and widening countries. 58% (7/12) of responding non-widening countries have a financial strategy on data management and 33% (4/12) of responding widening countries have a financial strategy as shown in Figure 33.

Figure 33: Non-widening and Widening Countries with a Financial Strategy on Data Management

Financial strategies on data management may include costs for data management of research projects, implementing DMPs, data services for research projects, capacity building for data stewards, networks of data stewards, research repositories, and e-infrastructures. We see hereby an overlap with responses on data stewardship which falls under infrastructure. Some countries note a link to the development of the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC).

3.1.5. Financial Strategy on FAIR Data

The second main policy question on FAIR data in Survey 2023 is *Does your country have a financial strategy on FAIR data?* (Q10). 44% (14/32) of responding countries have a financial strategy as shown in Figure 34.

Figure 34: Countries with a Financial Strategy on FAIR Data

50% (12/24) of responding EU countries have a financial strategy on FAIR data as shown in Figure 35.

Figure 35: EU Countries with a Financial Strategy on FAIR Data

We see differing percentages for the non-widening and widening countries. 67% (8/12) of responding non-widening countries have a financial strategy on FAIR data and 33% (4/12) of responding widening countries have a financial strategy as shown in Figure 36.

Figure 36: Non-widening and Widening Countries with a Financial Strategy on FAIR Data

The management of FAIR data is incorporated in some countries into financial strategies on data management. Some countries again note a link to the development of EOSC.

3.1.6. Financial Strategy on Open Data

The second main policy question on open data in Survey 2023 is *Does your country have a financial strategy on open data?* (Q14). 31% (10/32) of responding countries have a financial strategy as shown in Figure 37.

Figure 37: Countries with a Financial Strategy on Open Data

33% (8/24) of responding EU countries have a financial strategy on open data as shown in Figure 38.

Figure 38: EU Countries with a Financial Strategy on Open Data

We see similar percentages for the non-widening and widening countries. 42% (5/12) of responding non-widening countries have a financial strategy on open data and 25% (3/12) of responding widening countries have a financial strategy as shown in Figure 39.

Figure 39: Non-widening and Widening Countries with a Financial Strategy on Open Data

The management of open data is incorporated in some countries into financial strategies on data management. Some countries once again note a link to the development of EOOSC.

3.2. Practices

3.2.1. National Monitoring on Data Management

The first main practice question on data management in Survey 2023 is *Does your country have a national monitoring on data management?* (Q53). 13% (4/32) of responding countries have a national monitoring as shown in Figure 40.

Figure 40: Countries with a National Monitoring on Data Management

12% (3/24) of responding EU countries have a national monitoring on data management as shown in Figure 41.

Figure 41: EU Countries with a National Monitoring on Data Management

We see differing percentages for the non-widening and widening countries. 25% (3/12) of responding non-widening countries have a national monitoring on data management and 0% (0/12) of responding widening countries have a national monitoring as shown in Figure 42.

Figure 42: Non-widening and Widening Countries with a National Monitoring on Data Management

One country has developed specific indicators for monitoring data management, another country is monitoring research data sets which have been published, and another country is monitoring data management together with a group of representatives from RPOs and RFOs.

3.2.2. National Monitoring on FAIR Data

The first main practice question on FAIR data in Survey 2023 is *Does your country have a national monitoring on FAIR data?* (Q57). 13% (4/32) of responding countries have a national monitoring as shown in Figure 43.

Figure 43: Countries with a National Monitoring on FAIR Data

8% (2/24) of responding EU countries have a national monitoring on FAIR data as shown in Figure 44.

Figure 44: EU Countries with a National Monitoring on FAIR Data

We see differing percentages for the non-widening and widening countries. 17% (2/12) of responding non-widening countries have a national monitoring on FAIR data and 0% (0/12) of responding widening countries have a national monitoring as shown in Figure 45.

Figure 45: Non-widening and Widening Countries with a National Monitoring on FAIR Data

The monitoring of FAIR data is carried out in some countries under the monitoring of data management and Open Science. Many countries have commented that the monitoring of FAIR data is not yet mature due to the absence of standards for the publication and assessment of FAIR data. It is not yet possible to search for and find FAIR data in many research repositories.

3.2.3. National Monitoring on Open Data

The first main practice question on open data in Survey 2023 is *Does your country have a national monitoring on open data?* (Q61). 19% (6/32) of responding countries have a national monitoring as shown in Figure 46.

Figure 46: Countries with a National Monitoring on Open Data

25% (6/24) of responding EU countries have a national monitoring on open data as shown in Figure 47.

Figure 47: EU Countries with a National Monitoring on Open Data

We see similar percentages for the non-widening and widening countries. 25% (3/12) of responding non-widening countries have a national monitoring on open data and 25% (3/12) of responding widening countries have a national monitoring as shown in Figure 48.

Figure 48: Non-widening and Widening Countries with a National Monitoring on Open Data

The monitoring of open data may be carried out under the monitoring of data management and Open Science. A recurring comment to questions on data is that countries may focus on FAIR data rather than on open data even though they are not necessarily mutually exclusive.

3.2.4. National Investments in Data Management

The second main practice question on data management in Survey 2023 is *How much did your country financially invest in data management in 2022 in millions of Euros?* (Q55). 84% (27/32) of responding countries are not investing or have not stated the amount of investments in data management. 6% (2/32) of countries invested from above 0 to 50 €K, 3% (1/32) from 50 to 100

€K, and 3% (1/32) from 100 to 250 €K per 1000 FTE researchers as shown in Figure 49. One country hereby has invested in data management but has not provided official figures on the number of FTE researchers in the country in Eurostat.

Figure 49: Countries with National Investments in Data Management per 1000 FTE Researchers

There are limited investments or limited data on investments in data management across responding EU countries. 88% (21/24) are not investing or have not stated the amount of investments in data management. 8% (2/24) of EU countries invested from above 0 to 50 €K and 4% (1/24) from 50 to 100 €K per 1000 FTE researchers as shown in Figure 50.

Figure 50: EU Countries with National Investments in Data Management per 1000 FTE Researchers

We see low investments in data management for the responding non-widening and widening countries. The non-widening countries show investments from above 0 to 100 €K per 1000 FTE researchers while the widening countries show investments only from above 0 to 50 to €K per 1000 FTE researchers as shown in Figure 51.

Figure 51: Non-widening and Widening Countries with National Investments in Data Management per 1000 FTE Researchers

Survey respondents have noted that it is difficult to calculate the (exact) amount of investments in data management due to limited or no data being available, it is difficult to disentangle investments in data management from investments in FAIR data and open data, and it is difficult to disentangle investments in data management and research in general.

3.2.5. National Investments in FAIR Data

The second main practice question on FAIR data in Survey 2023 is *How much did your country financially invest in FAIR data in 2022 in millions of Euros?* (Q59). 91% (29/32) of responding countries are not investing or have not stated the amount of investments in FAIR data. 6% (2/32) of countries invested from above 0 to 50 €K per 1000 FTE researchers as shown in Figure 52. One country hereby has invested in FAIR data but has not provided official figures on the number of FTE researchers in the country in Eurostat.

Figure 52: Countries with National Investments in FAIR Data per 1000 FTE Researchers

There are limited investments or limited data on investments in FAIR data across responding EU countries. 92% (22/24) are not investing or have not stated the amount of investments in

FAIR data. 8% (2/24) of EU countries invested from above 0 to 50 €K per 1000 FTE researchers as shown in Figure 53.

Figure 53: EU Countries with National Investments in FAIR Data per 1000 FTE Researchers

We see similar low investments in FAIR data for the responding non-widening and widening countries. Both the non-widening and widening countries show investments from above 0 to 50 €K per 1000 FTE researchers as shown in Figure 54.

Figure 54: Non-widening and Widening Countries with National Investments in FAIR Data per 1000 FTE Researchers

Survey respondents have noted that it is difficult to calculate the (exact) amount of investments in FAIR data due to limited or no data being available, it is difficult to disentangle investments in FAIR data from investments in data management and open data, and it is difficult to disentangle investments in FAIR data and research in general.

3.2.6. National Investments in Open Data

The second main practice question on open data in Survey 2023 is *How much did your country financially invest in open data in 2022 in millions of Euros?* (Q63). 84% (27/32) of responding countries are not investing or have not stated the amount of investments in open data. 6%

(2/32) of countries invested from above 0 to 50 €K, 3% (1/32) from 50 to 100 €K, and 3% (1/32) from 100 to 250 €K per 1000 FTE researchers as shown in Figure 55. One country hereby has invested in open data but has not provided official figures on the number of FTE researchers in the country in Eurostat.

Figure 55: Countries with National Investments in Open Data per 1000 FTE Researchers

There are limited investments or limited data on investments in open data across responding EU countries. 83% (20/24) are not investing or have not stated the amount of investments in open data. 8% (2/24) of EU countries invested from above 0 to 50 €K, 4% (1/24) from 50 to 100 €K, and 4% (1/24) from 100 to 250 €K per 1000 FTE researchers as shown in Figure 56.

Figure 56: EU Countries with National Investments in Open Data per 1000 FTE Researchers

We see low investments in open data for the responding non-widening and widening countries. The non-widening countries show limited investments from above 0 to 100 €K per 1000 FTE researchers while the widening countries show limited investments from above 0 to 50 €K and 100 to 250 €K per 1000 FTE researchers as shown in Figure 57.

Figure 57: Non-widening and Widening Countries with National Investments in Open Data per 1000 FTE Researchers

Survey respondents have again noted that it is difficult to calculate the (exact) amount of investments in open data due to limited or no data being available, it is difficult to disentangle investments in open data from investments in data management and FAIR data, and it is difficult to disentangle investments in open data and research in general. Staff hired to manage open data initiatives at national level have been included in the investments.

4. Software

4.1. Policies

4.1.1. National Policy on Open Source Software

The first main policy question on open source software in Survey 2023 is *Does your country have a national policy on open source software?* (Q17) followed by *Is this policy mandatory?* (Q17.1). 28% (9/32) of responding countries have a national policy whereby 0% (0/9) of those policies are mandatory as shown in Figure 58.

Figure 58: Countries with a National Policy on Open Source Software

33% (8/24) of responding EU countries have a national policy on open source software whereby 0% (0/8) are mandatory as shown in Figure 59.

Figure 59: EU Countries with a National Policy on Open Source Software

We see similar percentages for the non-widening and widening countries. 42% (5/12) of responding non-widening countries have a national policy on open source software whereby 0% (0/5) are mandatory and 25% (3/12) of responding widening countries have a national policy whereby 0% (0/3) are mandatory as shown in Figure 60.

Figure 60: Non-widening and Widening Countries with a National Policy on Open Source Software

Open source software is addressed in some countries as part of a larger national policy on data management and Open Science. Some countries do not have a national policy on open source software but note that open source software is supported in other laws and policies.

4.1.2. Financial Strategy on Open Source Software

The second main policy question on open source software in Survey 2023 is *Does your country have a financial strategy on open source software?* (Q18). 0% (0/32) of responding countries reported having a financial strategy. One country noted that there is a financial strategy on Open Science which may include costs for open source software.

4.2. Practices

4.2.1. National Monitoring on Open Source Software

The first main practice question on open source software in Survey 2023 is *Does your country have a national monitoring on open source software?* (Q65). 6% (2/32) of responding countries have a national monitoring as shown in Figure 61.

Figure 61: Countries with a National Monitoring on Open Source Software

8% (2/24) of responding EU countries have a national monitoring on open source software as shown in Figure 62.

Figure 62: EU Countries with a National Monitoring on Open Source Software

We see differing percentages for the non-widening and widening countries. 0% (0/12) of responding non-widening countries have a national monitoring on open source software and 17% (2/12) of responding widening countries have a national monitoring as shown in Figure 63.

Figure 63: Non-widening and Widening Countries with a National Monitoring on Open Source Software

Some countries do not have a national monitoring on open source software but note that statistics on open source software are being collected by RPOs and repositories through CRIS and by aggregators which are looking beyond research at public sector open source software.

4.2.2. National Investments in Open Source Software

The second main practice question on open source software in Survey 2023 is *How much did your country financially invest in open source software in 2022 in millions of Euros?* (Q67). 81% (26/32) of responding countries are not investing or have not stated the amount of investments in open source software. 16% (5/32) of countries invested from above 0 to 50 €K and 3% (1/32) from 50 to 100 €K per 1000 FTE researchers as shown in Figure 64.

Figure 64: Countries with National Investments in Open Source Software per 1000 FTE Researchers

There are some investments or some reported data on investments in open source software across responding EU countries. 79% (19/24) are not investing or have not stated the amount of investments in open source software. 17% (4/24) of EU countries invested from above 0 to 50 €K and 4% (1/24) from 50 to 100 €K per 1000 FTE researchers as shown in Figure 65.

Figure 65: EU Countries with National Investments in Open Source Software per 1000 FTE Researchers

We see low investments in open source software for the responding non-widening and widening countries. The non-widening countries show limited investments from above 0 to 50 €K per 1000 FTE researchers while the widening countries show limited investments from above 0 to 100 €K per 1000 FTE researchers as shown in Figure 66.

Figure 66: Non-widening and Widening Countries with National Investments in Open Source Software per 1000 FTE Researchers

Many countries have noted that it is not possible or not easy to collect (reliable) national and institutional data on open source software, that direct funding for open source software may be minimal while funded projects may nevertheless indirectly produce open source software, and that funding for open source software may be provided within a wider package of research funding (such as investments in data management and Open Science). One country does not specify their investments but notes that investments in open source software in the country may go beyond research and the research sector and may total in billions of Euros.

5. Services

5.1. Policies

5.1.1. National Policy on Offering Services through EOSC

The first main policy question on offering services through EOSC in Survey 2023 is *Does your country have a national policy on offering services through EOSC?* (Q21) followed by *Is this policy mandatory?* (Q21.1). Offering services through EOSC hereby refers to ensuring that research services are made available in EOSC-Exchange [21] to serve the needs of researchers and research communities. We note that this definition will likely change in future surveys as the concepts of EOSC-Core [22] and EOSC-Exchange have in the meantime been replaced by the EOSC EU Node [23] and future contributions to EOSC are foreseen by enrolling an EOSC Node into the EOSC Federation or by onboarding resources to an EOSC Node. 22% (7/32) of responding countries have a national policy whereby 29% (2/7) of those policies are mandatory as shown in Figure 67.

Figure 67: Countries with a National Policy on Offering Services through EOSC

25% (6/24) of responding EU countries have a national policy on offering services through EOSC whereby 17% (1/6) are mandatory as shown in Figure 68.

Figure 68: EU Countries with a National Policy on Offering Services through EOSC

We see differing percentages for the non-widening and widening countries. 33% (4/12) of responding non-widening countries have a national policy on offering services through EOSC whereby 0% (0/4) are mandatory and 17% (2/12) of responding widening countries have a national policy whereby 50% (1/2) are mandatory as shown in Figure 69.

Figure 69: Non-widening and Widening Countries with a National Policy on Offering Services through EOSC

Offering services through EOSC is addressed in some countries as part of a larger national policy on data management and Open Science. Some countries do not have a national policy on offering services through EOSC but note that national organisations may require their services to be compliant with EOSC and that the choice for EOSC is left to service providers.

5.1.2. Financial Strategy on Offering Services through EOSC

The second main policy question on offering services through EOSC in Survey 2023 is *Does your country have a financial strategy on offering services through EOSC?* (Q22). 19% (6/32) of responding countries have a financial strategy as shown in Figure 70.

Figure 70: Countries with a Financial Strategy on Offering Services through EOSC

25% (6/24) of responding EU countries have a financial strategy on offering services through EOSC as shown in Figure 71.

Figure 71: EU Countries with a Financial Strategy on Offering Services through EOSC

We see differing percentages for the non-widening and widening countries. 17% (2/12) of responding non-widening countries and 33% (4/12) of responding widening countries have a financial strategy on offering services through EOSC as shown in Figure 72.

Figure 72: Non-widening and Widening Countries with a Financial Strategy on Offering Services through EOSC

Offering services through EOSC may be integrated in some countries into a larger financial strategy which supports the implementation of data infrastructures and data management.

5.2. Practices

5.2.1. National Monitoring on Offering Services through EOSC

The first main practice question on offering services through EOSC in Survey 2023 is *Does your country have a national monitoring on offering services through EOSC?* (Q69). 6% (2/32) of responding countries have a national monitoring as shown in Figure 73.

Figure 73: Countries with a National Monitoring on Offering Services through EOOSC

4% (1/24) of responding EU countries have a national monitoring on offering services through EOOSC as shown in Figure 74.

Figure 74: EU Countries with a National Monitoring on Offering Services through EOOSC

We see similar percentages for the non-widening and widening countries. 0% (0/12) of responding non-widening countries have a national monitoring on offering services through EOOSC and 8% (1/12) of responding widening countries have a national monitoring as shown in Figure 75.

Figure 75: Non-widening and Widening Countries with a National Monitoring on Offering Services through EOSC

One country notes that the monitoring on offering services through EOSC takes place within a larger national monitoring on Open Science. Some countries which do not have a national monitoring on offering services through EOSC note that they focus on making data FAIR rather than on offering services through EOSC and that data infrastructures are responsible for monitoring their services and thus any services which they may be offering through EOSC.

5.2.2. National Investments in Offering Services through EOSC

The second main practice question on offering services through EOSC in Survey 2023 is *How much did your country financially invest in offering services through EOSC in 2022 in millions of Euros?* (Q71). 91% (29/32) of responding countries are not investing or have not stated the amount of investments in offering services through EOSC. 6% (2/32) of countries invested from above 0 to 50 €K while 3% (1/32) show outlier investments from 1000 to 1500 €K per 1000 FTE researchers as shown in Figure 76.

Figure 76: Countries with National Investments in Offering Services through EOSC per 1000 FTE Researchers

There are limited investments or limited data on investments in offering services through EOSC across responding EU countries in. 88% (21/24) are not investing or have not stated the amount of investments in data management. 8% (2/24) of EU countries invested from above 0 to 50 €K and 3% (1/24) from 1000 to 1500 €K per 1000 FTE researchers as shown in Figure 77.

Figure 77: EU Countries with National Investments in Offering Services through EOSC per 1000 FTE Researchers

We see differing investments in offering services through EOSC for the responding non-widening and widening countries. The non-widening countries show no investments while the widening countries show investments from above 0 to 50 €K and from 1000 to 1500 €K per 1000 FTE researchers as shown in Figure 78.

Figure 78: Non-widening and Widening Countries with National Investments in Offering Services through EOSC per 1000 FTE Researchers

Many countries have noted that it is currently not possible or not easy to collect (reliable) national data on investments in offering services through EOSC.

6. Infrastructure

6.1. Policies

6.1.1. National Policy on Connecting Repositories to EOSC

The first main policy question on offering services through EOSC in Survey 2023 is *Does your country have a national policy on connecting repositories to EOSC?* (Q25) followed by *Is this policy mandatory?* (Q25.1). Connecting repositories to EOSC hereby refers to ensuring that repositories make their research outputs discoverable through EOSC. It remains to be seen how responses to this or a similar question may change in future surveys as a result of the uptake of the EOSC Federation. 19% (6/32) of responding countries have a national policy whereby 67% (4/6) of those policies are mandatory as shown in Figure 79.

Figure 79: Countries with a National Policy on Connecting Repositories to EOSC

21% (5/24) of responding EU countries have a national policy on connecting repositories to EOSC whereby 80% (4/5) are mandatory as shown in Figure 80.

Figure 80: EU Countries with a National Policy on Connecting Repositories to EOSC

We see differing percentages for the non-widening and widening countries. 8% (1/12) of responding non-widening countries have a national policy on connecting repositories to EOSC whereby 100% (1/1) are mandatory and 33% (4/12) of responding widening countries have a national policy whereby 75% (3/4) are mandatory as shown in Figure 81.

Figure 81: Non-widening and Widening Countries with a National Policy on Connecting Repositories to EOSC

One country notes that a national trusted data repository is aligning with EOSC by implementing services which are compatible with EOSC Authentication and Authorisation Infrastructure (AAI) and Persistent Identifier (PID) policies as well as continuously adopting to interoperability requirements for EOSC. Some countries do not have a national policy on connecting repositories to EOSC but are utilising OpenAIRE to support interoperability with and onboarding into EOSC. Several countries note that future activities for EOSC are planned.

6.1.2. National Policy on Data Stewardship

The first main policy question on data stewardship in Survey 2023 is *Does your country have a national policy on data stewardship?* (Q29) followed by *Is this policy mandatory?* (Q29.1). A data steward hereby refers to a professional data steward who supports researchers in their research data management. 28% (9/32) of responding countries have a national policy whereby 11% (1/9) of those policies are mandatory as shown in Figure 82.

Figure 82: Countries with a National Policy on Data Stewardship

33% (8/24) of responding EU countries have a national policy on data stewardship whereby 12% (1/8) are mandatory as shown in Figure 83.

Figure 83: EU Countries with a National Policy on Data Stewardship

We see differing percentages for the non-widening and widening countries. 42% (5/12) of responding non-widening countries have a national policy on data stewardship whereby 0% (0/5) are mandatory and 25% (3/12) of responding widening countries have a national policy whereby 33% (1/3) are mandatory as shown in Figure 84.

Figure 84: Non-widening and Widening Countries with a National Policy on Data Stewardship

Countries without a policy on data stewardship note that there are national activities (such as the creation of a national working group related to EOSC) and organisational activities (such as the creation of a university course) on data stewardship and that there are future plans for data stewardship. Some countries note that they would consider data stewardship to fall under the survey category of data or skills/training rather than under infrastructure.

6.1.3. National Policy on Long-term Data Preservation

The first main policy question on long-term data preservation in Survey 2023 is *Does your country have a national policy on long-term data preservation?* (Q33) followed by *Is this policy mandatory?* (Q33.1). Long-term data preservation hereby refers to ensuring that digital or physical access is provided (taking legitimate interests and constraints into account) to data or other results needed for the validation of the conclusions of peer-reviewed research

publications for a substantial period of time (with a minimum of at least 5 years and preferably 10 years) or longer according to disciplinary deposition practices. 25% (8/32) of responding countries have a national policy whereby 25% (2/8) of those policies are mandatory as shown in Figure 85.

Figure 85: Countries with a National Policy on Long-term Data Preservation

25% (6/24) of responding EU countries have a national policy on long-term data preservation whereby 17% (1/6) are mandatory as shown in Figure 86.

Figure 86: EU Countries with a National Policy on Long-term Data Preservation

We see differing percentages for the non-widening and widening countries. 42% (5/12) of responding non-widening countries have a national policy on long-term data preservation whereby 0% (0/5) are mandatory and 8% (1/12) of responding widening countries have a national policy whereby 100% (1/1) are mandatory as shown in Figure 87.

Figure 87: Non-widening and Widening Countries with a National Policy on Long-term Data Preservation

Countries without a policy on long-term data preservation comment that long-term data preservation may be carried out in national archives and repositories or may be indirectly addressed in other laws and regulations (such as on IT security and data management) or other policies (such as on preservation of publications and underlying data in repositories).

6.1.4. Financial Strategy on Connecting Repositories to EOSC

The second main policy question on connecting repositories to EOSC in Survey 2023 is *Does your country have a financial strategy on connecting repositories to EOSC?* (Q26). 16% (5/32) of responding countries have a financial strategy as shown in Figure 88.

Figure 88: Countries with a Financial Strategy on Connecting Repositories to EOSC

21% (5/24) of responding EU countries have a financial strategy on connecting repositories to EOSC as shown in Figure 89.

Figure 89: EU Countries with a Financial Strategy on Connecting Repositories to EOSC

We see differing percentages for the non-widening and widening countries. 1% (1/12) of responding non-widening countries and 33% (4/12) of responding widening countries have a financial strategy on connecting repositories to EOSC as shown in Figure 90.

Figure 90: Non-widening and Widening Countries with a Financial Strategy on Connecting Repositories to EOSC

Some countries note that they do not have a financial strategy on connecting repositories to EOSC but are investing in repositories including support for human resources and interoperability with EOSC. It is noteworthy that many countries have organisations which are paying (mandated) members of the EOSC Association (and thus intend to connect to EOSC).

6.1.5. Financial Strategy on Data Stewardship

The second main policy question on data stewardship in Survey 2023 is *Does your country have a financial strategy on data stewardship?* (Q30). 25% (8/32) of responding countries have a financial strategy as shown in Figure 91.

Figure 91: Countries with a Financial Strategy on Data Stewardship

29% (7/24) of responding EU countries have a financial strategy on data stewardship as shown in Figure 92.

Figure 92: EU Countries with a Financial Strategy on Data Stewardship

We see similar percentages for the non-widening and widening countries. 33% (4/12) of responding non-widening countries and 25% (3/12) of responding widening countries have a financial strategy on data stewardship as shown in Figure 93.

Figure 93: Non-widening and Widening Countries with a Financial Strategy on Data Stewardship

Some countries note that the investments in data stewardship fall under a more general financial strategy on Open Science, the implementation of EOSC, and data management.

6.1.6. Financial Strategy on Long-term Data Preservation

The second main policy question on long-term data preservation in Survey 2023 is *Does your country have a financial strategy on long-term data preservation?* (Q34). 19% (6/32) of responding countries have a financial strategy as shown in Figure 94.

Figure 94: Countries with a Financial Strategy on Long-term Data Preservation

17% (4/24) of responding EU countries have a financial strategy on long-term data preservation as shown in Figure 95.

Figure 95: EU Countries with a Financial Strategy on Long-term Data Preservation

We see similar percentages for the non-widening and widening countries. 17% (2/12) of responding non-widening countries and 17% (2/12) of responding widening countries have a financial strategy on long-term data preservation as shown in Figure 96.

Figure 96: Non-widening and Widening Countries with a Financial Strategy on Long-term Data Preservation

Long-term data preservation is included in wider financial strategies on data management or the provision of long-term services and infrastructure for open data in some countries.

6.2. Practices

6.2.1. National Monitoring on Connecting Repositories to EOSC

The first main practice question on connecting repositories to EOSC in Survey 2023 is *Does your country have a national monitoring on connecting repositories to EOSC?* (Q73). 3% (1/32) of responding countries have a national monitoring as shown in Figure 97.

Figure 97: Countries with a National Monitoring on Connecting Repositories to EOSC

0% (0/24) of responding EU countries reported having a national monitoring on connecting repositories to EOSC. One country noted that the national monitoring on connecting repositories to EOSC falls under a national programme on Open Science.

6.2.2. National Monitoring on Data Stewardship

The first main practice question on data stewardship in Survey 2023 is *Does your country have a national monitoring on data stewardship?* (Q77). 6% (2/32) of responding countries have a national monitoring as shown in Figure 98.

Figure 98: Countries with a National Monitoring on Data Stewardship

4% (1/24) of responding EU countries have a national monitoring on data stewardship as shown in Figure 99.

Figure 99: EU Countries with a National Monitoring on Data Stewardship

We see similar low percentages for the non-widening and widening countries. 8% (1/12) of responding non-widening countries have a national monitoring on data stewardship and 0% (0/12) of responding widening countries have a national monitoring as shown in Figure 100.

Figure 100: Non-widening and Widening Countries with a National Monitoring on Data Stewardship

National monitoring on data stewardship falls in some countries under the monitoring of a national programme on Open Science or the implementation of FAIR data management.

6.2.3. National Monitoring on Long-term Data Preservation

The first main practice question on long-term data preservation in Survey 2023 is *Does your country have a national monitoring on long-term data preservation?* (Q81). 9% (3/32) of responding countries have a national monitoring as shown in Figure 101.

Figure 101: Countries with a National Monitoring on Long-term Data Preservation

8% (2/24) of responding EU countries have a national monitoring on long-term data preservation as shown in Figure 102.

Figure 102: EU Countries with a National Monitoring on Long-term Data Preservation

We see the same low percentages for the non-widening and widening countries. 8% (1/12) of responding non-widening countries have a national monitoring on long-term data preservation and 8% (1/12) of responding widening countries have a national monitoring as shown in Figure 103.

Figure 103: Non-widening and Widening Countries with a National Monitoring on Long-term Data Preservation

National monitoring on long-term data preservation falls in one country under the monitoring of a national programme on Open Science. Another country without national monitoring on long-term data preservation notes that the majority of research software developed in the country is likely developed in GitHub and preserved in Zenodo and Software Heritage.

6.2.4. National Investments in Connecting Repositories to EOSC

The second main practice question on connecting repositories to EOSC in Survey 2023 is *How much did your country financially invest in connecting repositories to EOSC in 2022 in millions of Euros?* (Q75). 81% (26/32) of responding countries are not investing or have not stated the amount of investments in connecting repositories to EOSC. 13% (4/32) of countries invested from above 0 to 50 €K, 3% (1/32) from 50 to 100 €K, and 3% (1/32) from 250 to 500 €K per 1000 FTE researchers as shown in Figure 104.

Figure 104: Countries with National Investments in Connecting Repositories to EOSC per 1000 FTE Researchers

There are limited investments or limited data on investments in connecting repositories to EOSC across responding EU countries. 79% (19/24) are not investing or have not stated the amount of investments in connecting repositories to EOSC. 13% (3/24) of EU countries

invested from above 0 to 50 €K, 4% (1/24) from 50 to 100 €K, and 4% (1/24) from 250 to 500 €K per 1000 FTE researchers as shown in Figure 105.

Figure 105: EU Countries with National Investments in Connecting Repositories to EOSC per 1000 FTE Researchers

We see differing low investments or lack of data on investments in connecting repositories to EOSC for the responding non-widening and widening countries. The non-widening countries show some investments from above 0 to 50 €K per 1000 FTE researchers while the widening countries show a mix of low investments from 0 to 100 €K and 250 to 500 €K per 1000 FTE researchers as shown in Figure 106.

Figure 106: Non-widening and Widening Countries with National Investments in Connecting Repositories to EOSC per 1000 FTE Researchers

Some countries note that their figures for investments in connecting repositories to EOSC are based on investments in research infrastructures which have the potential to connect to EOSC (such as CERN, ESFRI, EuroHPC Joint Undertaking, and SESAME). One country notes that their priority is to ensure technical and semantic interoperability which follows the FAIR principles rather than to register repositories in the EOSC Portal. Some countries again note that they are not yet monitoring or able to monitor investments in connecting repositories to EOSC.

6.2.5. National Investments in Data Stewardship

The second main practice question on data stewardship in Survey 2023 is *How much did your country financially invest in data stewardship in 2022 in millions of Euros?* (Q79). 91% (29/32) of responding countries are not investing or have not stated the amount of investments in data stewardship. 9% (3/32) of countries invested from above 0 to 50 €K per 1000 FTE researchers as shown in Figure 107.

Figure 107: Countries with National Investments in Data Stewardship per 1000 FTE Researchers

There are limited investments or limited data on investments in data stewardship across responding EU countries. 92% (22/24) are not investing or have not stated the amount of investments in data stewardship. 8% (2/24) of EU countries invested from above 0 to 50 €K per 1000 FTE researchers as shown in Figure 108.

Figure 108: EU Countries with National Investments in Data Stewardship per 1000 FTE Researchers

We see similar low investments in data stewardship for the responding non-widening and widening countries. Both the non-widening and widening countries show low investments from above 0 to 50 €K per 1000 FTE researchers as shown in Figure 109.

Figure 109: Non-widening and Widening Countries with National Investments in Data Stewardship per 1000 FTE Researchers

One country noted that they are investing in projects on data stewardship whereby they only finance up to 50% of the projects, with the remainder of the budget financed by the project organisations. Many countries have noted that it is currently not possible to collect (reliable) national data (from organisations in their countries) on investments in data stewardship.

6.2.6. National Investments in Long-term Data Preservation

The second main practice question on long-term data preservation in Survey 2023 is *How much did your country financially invest in long-term data preservation in 2022 in millions of Euros?* (Q83). 91% (29/32) of responding countries are not investing or have not stated the amount of investments in long-term data preservation. 3% (1/32) of countries invested from above 0 to 50 €K, 3% (1/32) from 50 to 100 €K, and 3% (1/32) from 100 to 250 €K per 1000 FTE researchers as shown in Figure 110.

Figure 110: Countries with National Investments in Long-term Data Preservation per 1000 FTE Researchers

There are limited investments or limited data on investments in long-term data preservation across responding EU countries. 92% (22/24) are not investing or have not stated the amount

of investments in long-term data preservation. 4% (1/24) of EU countries invested from above 0 to 50 €K and 4% (1/24) from 50 to 100 €K per 1000 FTE researchers as shown in Figure 111.

Figure 111: EU Countries with National Investments in Long-term Data Preservation per 1000 FTE Researchers

We see similar low investments in long-term data preservation for the responding non-widening and widening countries. The non-widening countries show few investments from above 0 to 50 €K per 1000 FTE researchers while the widening countries show few investments from 50 to 100 €K per 1000 FTE researchers as shown in Figure 112.

Figure 112: Non-widening and Widening Countries with National Investments in Long-term Data Preservation per 1000 FTE Researchers

Many countries have simply noted that it is currently not possible to collect (reliable) national data (from organisations in their countries) on investments in long-term data preservation.

7. Skills/training

7.1. Policies

7.1.1. National Policy on Skills/training for Open Science

The first main policy question on skills/training for Open Science in Survey 2023 is *Does your country have a national policy on skills/training for Open Science?* (Q37) followed by *Is this policy mandatory?* (Q37.1). 47% (15/32) of responding countries have a national policy whereby 0% (0/15) of those policies are mandatory as shown in Figure 113.

Figure 113: Countries with a National Policy on Skills/training for Open Science

54% (13/24) of responding EU countries have a national policy on skills/training for Open Science whereby 0% (0/13) are mandatory as shown in Figure 114.

Figure 114: EU Countries with a National Policy on Skills/training for Open Science

We see similar percentages for the non-widening and widening countries. 50% (6/12) of responding non-widening countries have a national policy on skills/training for Open Science whereby 0% (0/6) are mandatory and 58% (7/12) of responding widening countries have a national policy whereby 0% (0/7) are mandatory as shown in Figure 115.

Figure 115: Non-widening and Widening Countries with a National Policy on Skills/training for Open Science

Countries with a national policy on skills/training for Open Science note that skills for data management, open data, and Open Science are included in national strategies and action plans for Open Science. One country highlights that teachers in higher education institutions are required to have open access skills. Some countries without a policy note that skills/training for Open Science are being implemented at universities and university libraries.

7.1.2. Financial Strategy on Skills/training for Open Science

The second main policy question on skills/training for Open Science in Survey 2023 is *Does your country have a financial strategy on skills/training for Open Science?* (Q38). 28% (9/32) of responding countries have a financial strategy as shown in Figure 116.

Figure 116: Countries with a Financial Strategy on Skills/training for Open Science

33% (8/24) of responding EU countries have a financial strategy on skills/training for Open Science as shown in Figure 117.

Figure 117: EU Countries with a Financial Strategy on Skills/training for Open Science

We see differing percentages for the non-widening and widening countries. 25% (3/12) of responding non-widening countries and 42% (5/12) of responding widening countries have a financial strategy on skills/training for Open Science as shown in Figure 118.

Figure 118: Non-widening and Widening Countries with a Financial Strategy on Skills/training for Open Science

Some countries with a financial strategy note that skills/training for Open Science are included in investments in EOSC, funding programmes aimed at the skills/training of early-career researchers, and supporting data competence centres and data steward networks. It should be noted that skills/training for Open Science may include a (mix of a) variety of topics such as skills/training for open access to publications, data management, and open source software.

7.2. Practices

7.2.1. National Monitoring on Skills/training for Open Science

The first main practice question on skills/training for Open Science in Survey 2023 is *Does your country have a national monitoring on skills/training for Open Science?* (Q85). 16% (5/32) of responding countries have a national monitoring as shown in Figure 119.

Figure 119: Countries with a National Monitoring on Skills/training for Open Science

17% (4/24) of responding EU countries have a national monitoring on skills/training for Open Science as shown in Figure 120.

Figure 120: EU Countries with a National Monitoring on Skills/training for Open Science

We see the same percentages for the non-widening and widening countries. 17% (2/12) of responding non-widening countries have a national monitoring on skills/training for Open Science and 17% (2/12) of responding widening countries have a national monitoring as shown in Figure 121.

Figure 121: Non-widening and Widening Countries with a National Monitoring on Skills/training for Open Science

Several countries with a national monitoring note that skills/training for Open Science are monitored within the wider monitoring of the national implementation of Open Science. One country without a national monitoring on skills/training for Open Science comments that there is instead a national monitoring on skills/training for FAIR data and data stewardship.

7.2.2. National Investments in Skills/training for Open Science

The second main practice question on skills/training for Open Science in Survey 2023 is *How much did your country financially invest in skills/training for Open Science in 2022 in millions of Euros?* (Q87). 84% (27/32) of responding countries are not investing or have not stated the amount of investments in skills/training for Open Science. 16% (5/32) of countries invested from above 0 to 50 €K per 1000 FTE researchers as shown in Figure 122.

Figure 122: Countries with National Investments in Skills/training for Open Science per 1000 FTE Researchers

There are some investments in skills/training for Open Science across responding EU countries. 83% (20/24) are not investing or have not stated the amount of investments in skills/training for Open Science. 17% (4/24) of EU countries invested from above 0 to 50 €K per 1000 FTE researchers as shown in Figure 123.

Figure 123: EU Countries with National Investments in Skills/training for Open Science per 1000 FTE Researchers

We see similar low investments in skills/training for Open Science for the responding non-widening and widening countries. Both the non-widening and widening countries show few investments from above 0 to 50 €K per 1000 FTE researchers as shown in Figure 124.

Figure 124: Non-widening and Widening Countries with National Investments in Skills/training for Open Science per 1000 FTE Researchers

Some countries investing in skills/training for Open Science note that investments may support skills/training for data management, open education platforms, and data competence centres. Many countries note that it is currently not possible to collect (reliable) national data (from organisations in their countries) on investments in skills/training for Open Science.

8. Assessment

8.1. Policies

8.1.1. National Policy on Incentives/rewards for Open Science

The first main policy question on incentives/rewards for Open Science in Survey 2023 is *Does your country have a national policy on incentives/rewards for Open Science?* (Q41) followed by *Is this policy mandatory?* (Q41.1). 47% (15/32) of responding countries have a national policy whereby 20% (3/15) of those policies are mandatory as shown in Figure 125.

Figure 125: Countries with a National Policy on Incentives/rewards for Open Science

54% (13/24) of responding EU countries have a national policy on incentives/rewards for Open Science whereby 23% (3/13) are mandatory as shown in Figure 126.

Figure 126: EU Countries with a National Policy on Incentives/rewards for Open Science

We see differing percentages for the non-widening and widening countries. 67% (8/12) of responding non-widening countries have a national policy on incentives/rewards for Open Science whereby 25% (2/8) are mandatory and 42% (5/12) of responding widening countries have a national policy whereby 20% (1/5) are mandatory as shown in Figure 127.

Figure 127: Non-widening and Widening Countries with a National Policy on Incentives/rewards for Open Science

Many countries with a national policy note that incentives/rewards for Open Science are incorporated into their wider Open Science policies and strategies. One country notes that only openly available research results should be taken into account in research assessment. Many countries without a national policy are developing incentives/rewards for Open Science.

8.1.2. Financial Strategy on Incentives/rewards for Open Science

The second main policy question on incentives/rewards for Open Science in Survey 2023 is *Does your country have a financial strategy on incentives/rewards for Open Science?* (Q42). 22% (7/32) of responding countries have a financial strategy as shown in Figure 128.

Figure 128: Countries with a Financial Strategy on Incentives/rewards for Open Science

25% (6/24) of responding EU countries have a financial strategy on incentives/rewards for Open Science as shown in Figure 129.

Figure 129: EU Countries with a Financial Strategy on Incentives/rewards for Open Science

We see differing percentages for the non-widening and widening countries. 33% (4/12) of responding non-widening countries and 17% (2/12) of responding widening countries have a financial strategy on incentives/rewards for Open Science as shown in Figure 130.

Figure 130: Non-widening and Widening Countries with a Financial Strategy on Incentives/rewards for Open Science

Some countries with a financial strategy note that funding for incentives/rewards for Open Science falls under wider national programmes and strategies for Open Science. One country highlights that while there is no financial strategy there nevertheless are national investments to support incentives/rewards for Open Science. It is interesting that some countries are specifically focusing on incentives/rewards for open access publications and open data.

8.2. Practices

8.2.1. National Monitoring on Incentives/rewards for Open Science

The first main practice question on incentives/rewards for Open Science in Survey 2023 is *Does your country have a national monitoring on incentives/rewards for Open Science?* (Q89). 16% (5/32) of responding countries have a national monitoring as shown in Figure 131.

Figure 131: Countries with a National Monitoring on Incentives/rewards for Open Science

12% (3/24) of responding EU countries have a national monitoring on incentives/rewards for Open Science as shown in Figure 132.

Figure 132: EU Countries with a National Monitoring on Incentives/rewards for Open Science

We see differing percentages for the non-widening and widening countries. 25% (3/12) of responding non-widening countries have a national monitoring on incentives/rewards for Open Science and 0% (0/12) of responding widening countries have a national monitoring as shown in Figure 133.

Figure 133: Non-widening and Widening Countries with a National Monitoring on Incentives/rewards for Open Science

Some countries note that the monitoring of incentives/rewards for Open Science is carried out within the wider framework of monitoring the implementation of Open Science. One country is using indicators for responsible evaluation and bibliometrics for their monitoring. One country without a national monitoring highlights that they are following relevant initiatives and activities of the Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment (CoARA).

8.2.2. National Investments in Incentives/rewards for Open Science

The second main practice question on incentives/rewards for Open Science in Survey 2023 is *How much did your country financially invest in incentives/rewards for Open Science in 2022 in millions of Euros?* (Q91). 88% (28/32) of responding countries are not investing or have not stated the amount of investments in incentives/rewards for Open Science. 13% (4/32) of countries invested from above 0 to 50 €K per 1000 FTE researchers as shown in Figure 134. One country hereby invested a low amount in incentives/rewards for Open Science which becomes negligible when relativised per 1000 FTE researchers in the country.

Figure 134: Countries with National Investments in Incentives/rewards for Open Science per 1000 FTE Researchers

There are limited investments or limited data on investments in incentives/rewards for Open Science across responding EU countries. 88% (21/24) are not investing or have not stated the amount of investments in incentives/rewards for Open Science. 13% (3/24) of EU countries invested from above 0 to 50 €K per 1000 FTE researchers as shown in Figure 135.

Figure 135: EU Countries with National Investments in Incentives/rewards for Open Science per 1000 FTE Researchers

We see similar low investments in incentives/rewards for Open Science for the responding non-widening and widening countries. Both the non-widening and widening countries show few investments from above 0 to 50 €K per 1000 FTE researchers as shown in Figure 136.

Figure 136: Non-widening and Widening Countries with National Investments in Incentives/rewards for Open Science per 1000 FTE Researchers

Many countries without investments note that they are not yet able to collect (reliable) information on investments in incentives/rewards for Open Science. One country notes that it is not clear which investments should be included for incentives/rewards for Open Science.

9. Engagement

9.1. Policies

9.1.1. National Policy on Citizen Science

The first main policy question on citizen science in Survey 2023 is *Does your country have a national policy on citizen science?* (Q45) followed by *Is this policy mandatory?* (Q41.1). 44% (14/32) of responding countries have a national policy whereby 21% (3/14) of those policies are mandatory as shown in Figure 137.

Figure 137: Countries with a National Policy on Citizen Science

50% (12/24) of responding EU countries have a national policy on citizen science whereby 17% (2/12) are mandatory as shown in Figure 138.

Figure 138: EU Countries with a National Policy on Citizen Science

We see somewhat differing percentages for the non-widening and widening countries. 58% (7/12) of responding non-widening countries have a national policy on citizen science whereby 14% (1/7) are mandatory and 42% (5/12) of responding widening countries have a national policy whereby 20% (1/5) are mandatory as shown in Figure 139.

Figure 139: Non-widening and Widening Countries with a National Policy on Citizen Science

Many countries with a national policy note that citizen science is incorporated into wider policies on science, Open Science, EOSC, and science communication as well as in one case in a law on science, technology, and innovation. Some countries without a national policy note that funded projects are required or encouraged to engage the public and popularise science.

9.1.2. Financial Strategy on Citizen Science

The second main policy question on citizen science in Survey 2023 is *Does your country have a financial strategy on citizen science?* (Q46). 16% (5/32) of responding countries have a financial strategy as shown in Figure 140.

Figure 140: Countries with a Financial Strategy on Citizen Science

17% (4/24) of responding EU countries have a financial strategy on citizen science as shown in Figure 141.

Figure 141: EU Countries with a Financial Strategy on Citizen Science

We see differing percentages for the non-widening and widening countries. 25% (3/12) of responding non-widening countries and 8% (1/12) of responding widening countries have a financial strategy on citizen science as shown in Figure 142.

Figure 142: Non-widening and Widening Countries with a Financial Strategy on Citizen Science

Several countries with a financial strategy note that citizen science is included and funded in a wider strategy on science, technology, and innovation, an action plan for Open Science, and a strategy for public engagement. A few countries without a financial strategy comment that funding activities on citizen science are in development or are restricted to organisations.

9.2. Practices

9.2.1. National Monitoring on Citizen Science

The first main practice question on citizen science in Survey 2023 is *Does your country have a national monitoring on citizen science?* (Q93). 6% (2/32) of responding countries have a national monitoring as shown in Figure 143.

Figure 143: Countries with a National Monitoring on Citizen Science

4% (1/24) of responding EU countries have a national monitoring on citizen science as shown in Figure 144.

Figure 144: EU Countries with a National Monitoring on Citizen Science

We see similar low percentages for the non-widening and widening countries. 8% (1/12) of responding non-widening countries have a national monitoring on citizen science and 0% (0/12) of responding widening countries have a national monitoring as shown in Figure 145.

Figure 145: Non-widening and Widening Countries with a National Monitoring on Citizen Science

One country with a national monitoring notes that citizen science is monitored within wider programmes for Open Science and science popularisation. Another country with a national monitoring is implementing monitoring via an online citizen science observatory whereby the definition of citizen science is not fixed but is evolving with new forms of citizen engagement.

9.2.2. National Investments in Citizen Science

The second main practice question on citizen science in Survey 2023 is *How much did your country financially invest in citizen science in 2022 in millions of Euros?* (Q95). 81% (26/32) of responding countries are not investing or have not stated the amount of investments in citizen science. 16% (5/32) of countries invested from above 0 to 50 €K per 1000 FTE researchers as shown in Figure 146. One country has invested in citizen science but has not provided official figures on the number of FTE researchers in the country in Eurostat.

Figure 146: Countries with National Investments in Citizen Science per 1000 FTE Researchers

There are some investments in citizen science across responding EU countries. 79% (19/24) are not investing or have not stated the amount of investments in citizen science. 21% (5/24)

of EU countries invested from above 0 to 50 €K per 1000 FTE researchers as shown in Figure 147.

Figure 147: EU Countries with National Investments in Citizen Science per 1000 FTE Researchers

We see similar low investments in citizen science for the responding non-widening and widening countries. Both the non-widening and widening countries show some investments from above 0 to 50 €K per 1000 FTE researchers as shown in Figure 148.

Figure 148: Non-widening and Widening Countries with National Investments in Citizen Science per 1000 FTE Researchers

Many countries without national investments in citizen science note that they are not yet able to collect (reliable) information on investments in their countries in citizen science.

10. Total Investments in EOSC and Open Science

10.1. Total Investments in Millions of Euros

This report has so far looked at national investments across the eight categories relevant for EOSC and Open Science of publications, data, software, services, infrastructure, skills/training, assessment, and engagement. A general question on national investments in Survey 2023 is *How much did your country financially invest in total in EOSC and Open Science in 2022 in millions of Euros?* (Q99). 38% (12/32) of responding countries are not investing or have not stated their investments in EOSC and Open Science. The remaining countries show variety in the amount of their investments. 16% (5/32) of countries invested from above 0 to 1 €M, 16% (5/32) from 1 to 5 €M, 3% (1/32) from 5 to 10 €M, 16% (5/32) from 10 to 50 €M, 9% (3/32) from 50 to 100 €M, and 3% (1/32) from 100 to 150 €M in EOSC and Open Science as shown in Figure 149.

Figure 149: Countries with National Investments in EOSC and Open Science

The responding EU countries similarly show variety in their investments in EOSC and Open Science. 33% (8/24) of countries are not investing or have not reported their investments. 13% (3/24) of countries invested from above 0 to 1 €M, 17% (4/24) from 1 to 5 €M, 21% (5/24) from 10 to 50 €M, 13% (3/24) from 50 to 100 €M, and 4% (1/24) from 100 to 150 €M in EOSC and Open Science as shown in Figure 150.

Figure 150: EU Countries with National Investments in EOSC and Open Science

We see differing investments in EOSC and Open Science for the responding non-widening and widening countries. The non-widening countries show slightly more and higher investments across a wider range than the widening countries as shown in Figure 151.

Figure 151: Non-widening and Widening Countries with National Investments in EOSC and Open Science

The total national investments in EOSC and Open Science for a given country may be greater than the sum of the individual investments which have been reported in Survey 2023 for the eight categories relevant for EOSC and Open Science. This figure may, for instance, include specific national budgets for EOSC and Open Science and activities which extend beyond the activities reported in Survey 2023 such as national positions for staff supporting EOSC and Open Science. EOSC-SB also agreed to include in this figure 2% of their annual contributions to the European Strategy Forum on Research Infrastructures (ESFRI) and international research infrastructures. Several countries noted that they do not provide ear-marked or direct financial contributions to EOSC and Open Science at the national level and that they are currently unable to collect reliable data on national investments in EOSC and Open Science.

10.2. Total Investments per 1000 FTE Researchers

The figures reported in Survey 2023 for the general question *How much did your country financially invest in total in EOSC and Open Science in 2022 in millions of Euros?* (Q99) can be better compared across countries by being relativised to 1000 FTE researchers in the country. 38% (12/32) of responding countries are not investing or have not stated their investments in EOSC and Open Science. The remaining countries show variety in the amount of their investments per 1000 FTE researchers. 13% (4/32) of countries invested from above 0 to 50 €K, 9% (3/32) from 50 to 100 €K, 19% (6/32) from 100 to 250 €K, 9% (3/32) from 250 to 500 €K, 6% (2/32) from 500 to 1000 €K, and 3% (1/32) from 1000 to 1500 €K per 1000 FTE researchers in EOSC and Open Science as shown in Figure 152. One country has national investments but has not provided official figures on the number of FTE researchers in the country in Eurostat.

Figure 152: Countries with National Investments in EOSC and Open Science per 1000 FTE Researchers

The responding EU countries similarly show variety in the amount of their investments in EOSC and Open Science per 1000 FTE researchers. 33% (8/24) of countries are not investing or have not reported their investments. 8% (2/24) of countries invested from above 0 to 50 €K, 13% (3/24) from 50 to 100 €K, 21% (5/24) from 100 to 250 €K, 13% (3/24) from 250 to 500 €K, 8% (2/24) from 500 to 1000 €K, and 4% (1/24) from 1000 to 1500 €K per 1000 FTE researchers in EOSC and Open Science as shown in Figure 153.

Figure 153: EU Countries with National Investments in EOSC and Open Science per 1000 FTE Researchers

We see somewhat differing investments in EOSC and Open Science per 1000 FTE researchers for the responding non-widening and widening countries. The non-widening countries show slightly more and higher investments than the widening countries as shown in Figure 154.

Figure 154: Non-widening and Widening Countries with National Investments in EOSC and Open Science per 1000 FTE Researchers

The total national investments in EOSC and Open Science were relativised per 1000 FTE researchers (in terms of researcher employment hours) rather than per 1000 researchers (in terms of researcher head count) as the head count does not provide a comparable figure for how much time the researchers are actually working (due to the varying nature of full-time and part-time contracts). It should also be noted that there are wide discrepancies across the countries in the total number of researchers depending on the sizes of the countries whereby the smallest country has 1563 researchers and the largest country has 486011 researchers.

11. Trend Analysis of Open Access to Publications

11.1. Comparison across Policies and Practices

This report has thus far provided a separate analysis of each of the survey questions focusing on countries with a national policy, financial strategy, national monitoring, and investments for the categories of publications, data, software, services, infrastructure, skills/training, assessment, and engagement. We will now zoom in on open access to publications and compare the various policies, strategies, and monitoring for EU countries in Survey 2023.

EU countries are overall quite advanced in their policies for open access to publications as shown in Figure 155. We remind ourselves hereby that 89% (24/27) of EU countries responded to the survey. 87% (21/24) of responding EU countries have a national policy on open access to publications whereby 38% (8/21) of those policies are mandatory. Responding EU countries also show relatively high rates of adoption of specific policies on open access to publications. 54% (13/24) have policies on immediate open access to publications whereby 31% (4/13) are mandatory, 46% (11/24) have policies on retention of IPR whereby 55% (6/11) are mandatory, and 54% (13/24) have policies on open licensing whereby 31% (4/13) are mandatory.

Figure 155: Publication Policies in EU Countries

The high level of adoption of national policies on open access to publications by EU countries seems to be closely aligned with the implementation of a financial strategy and national monitoring on open access to publications as shown in Figure 156. The high adoption of 87% (21/24) of responding EU countries with a national policy is followed closely by 54% (13/24)

with a financial strategy and 46% (11/24) with a national monitoring on open access to publications. It should be noted hereby that having a national policy does not imply that a country should have a financial strategy and national monitoring. The results simply show that countries more often than not choose to deploy such policies, strategies, and monitoring.

Figure 156: Publication Policies and Practices in EU Countries

The non-widening and widening countries show some similarities in their policies on open access to publications as shown in Figure 157. We remind ourselves hereby that 100% (12/12) of non-widening and 80% (12/15) of widening countries responded to the survey. There is a high adoption of a national policy on open access to publications with 92% (11/12) for non-widening countries whereby 36% (4/11) are mandatory and 83% (10/12) for widening countries whereby 40% (4/10) are mandatory. The adoption of a policy on immediate open access to publications is also high with 58% (7/12) for non-widening countries whereby 29% (2/7) are mandatory and 50% (6/12) for widening countries whereby 33% (2/6) are mandatory.

The non-widening and widening countries differ in their policies on the retention of IPR on publications with 67% (8/12) for non-widening countries whereby 50% (4/8) are mandatory and 25% (3/12) for widening countries whereby 67% (2/3) are mandatory. The same is true for policies on the open licensing of publications with 75% (9/12) for non-widening countries whereby 33% (3/9) are mandatory and 33% (4/12) for widening countries whereby 25% (1/4) are mandatory. The widening countries seem thus to place less of a priority on developing policies for the retention of IPR and the open licensing of publications for researchers.

Figure 157: Publication Policies in Non-widening and Widening Countries

The non-widening and widening countries show similarities in having a national policy on open access to publications with 92% (11/12) for non-widening countries and 83% (10/12) for widening countries as shown in Figure 158. This policy is often supported by a financial strategy in 58% (7/12) of non-widening countries and 50% (6/12) of widening countries. There is a clear difference in national monitoring whereby 75% (9/12) of non-widening countries versus 17% (2/12) of widening countries further support the policies with national monitoring.

Figure 158: Publication Policies and Practices in Non-widening and Widening Countries

11.2. Comparison across Surveys 2022 to 2023

A comparison of policies for EU countries on open access to publications from 2022 to 2023 initially reveals that there is an increase across all policies including having a national policy, immediate open access, retention of IPR, and open licensing within one year as shown in Figure 159. We should recall that while 89% (24/27) of EU countries responded in both 2022 and 2023, different EU countries responded in both years. Whether there is thus an increase,

or if the increase is due to the different countries responding to Surveys 2022 and 2023, is not further analysed in this report. We hereby simply provide an overview of the progress.

Figure 159: Publication Policies for 2022 and 2023 in EU Countries

We see a slight increase when comparing EU countries with a national policy and financial strategy but a slight decrease in national monitoring between 2022 and 2023 as shown in Figure 160.

Figure 160: Publication Policies and Practices for 2022 and 2023 in EU Countries

A comparison of policies for non-widening and widening countries on open access to publications from 2022 to 2023 reveals a slight increase across all policies for non-widening countries, but status quo for a national policy and immediate open access as well as a decrease for retention of IPR and an increase for open licensing for widening countries as shown in Figure 161. We should once again recall the different country responses in 2022 and

2023 whereby 83% (10/12) of non-widening countries responded in 2022 versus 100% (12/12) in 2023 and 93% (14/15) of widening countries responded in 2022 versus 80% (12/15) in 2023.

Figure 161: Publication Policies for 2022 and 2023 in Non-widening and Widening Countries

A last comparison of main policies and practices for non-widening and widening countries shows an overall increase across all policies and practices for the non-widening countries, but status quo for a national policy, a slight increase for a financial strategy, and a decrease for a national monitoring for the widening countries as shown in Figure 162.

Figure 162: Publication Policies and Practices for 2022 and 2023 in Non-widening and Widening Countries

12. Conclusion

The response rate for Survey 2023 was quite high with 32 countries responding whereby 24 of the 27 EU countries and 8 non-EU countries responded to the survey. These are exactly the same figures as for Survey 2022 although slightly different countries responded to Survey 2022 versus Survey 2023. One of the main goals of the survey is to provide longitudinal monitoring of the national implementation of EOSC and Open Science in Europe. All 27 EU countries should thus be encouraged in future to consistently respond to the annual surveys.

Some concepts in the survey are still not interpreted commonly across the countries. This applies for 'research-performing organisation' whereby there are still differences in the types of organisations included in the responses. This also applies for 'services offered through EOSC' and 'connecting repositories to EOSC' due to recent changes and uncertainty with the new EOSC node structure. Such concepts may need to be further discussed in future surveys.

Some categories of EOSC and Open Science seem to be more mature and prioritised than other categories across countries. This applies generally for the policies and practices related to publications, data, skills/training, assessment, and engagement. There are also noticeable differences in some categories between the non-widening and widening countries. Future support and funding could focus on these discrepancies across the categories and countries.

The annual survey has since the beginning acknowledged that the survey and data collection are in an initial stage of implementation. Many countries have noted that there is currently no (available) data or it is not possible to collect (reliable) data for various categories of EOSC and Open Science. This means that collected survey data should for now be taken as a best-effort attempt by the responding countries and will improve in the future iterations of the survey.

This analysis of Survey 2023 presented the results of key policy and practice questions on national policies, financial strategies, national monitoring, and national investments with a focus on EU countries and non-widening versus widening countries in the EU. The results of other questions and individual countries can be found in the EOSC Open Science Observatory.

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